

IMPACT OF CINEMATIC CRIME (NETFLIX SERIES AND MOVIES) ON YOUTH

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Abstract

The study at hand "Impact of Cinematic crime (Netflix Series and Movies) on Youth" is a quantitative research aimed at exploring how movies and series on Netflix show criminal and evil activities as heroic and afterwards their effects on the minds of young individual aged 15-25years. It investigates the influence of these negative characters that are being watched by the youngsters and eventually affects their behavior. In this study, it has been found out that crime series and movies shown on Netflix have negative affect on the youth psychologically. It also promotes aggression and depression in society. As they idealize criminals as their heroes. The study used survey method for data collection through a questionnaire using convenient sampling of 100 respondents with the application of "Cultivation Theory". The result shows that the content of the crime movies and portrayal of criminal activities as heroic is modelled and imitated by youth. It's also increasing aggression and depression in youth. The study also encourages showing the positive content to the viewers of Netflix as its most viewers are young generation.

Key words: *Influence, Cinematic Crime, Youngsters, Impact, Series, Movies*

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Introduction

Media represents our culture and it shows what and how society works. Media, whether it's print, electronic or digital, is the only tool that helps to educate people. Today the media has become the face of our society. There is a range of media outlets that have influenced the thoughts of the young generation and other parts of our society (Nity and Gaurav, 2017). Serials and films play the role of the construction and makeup of the society and its culture. The web series depicts the society and affects beyond the boundaries of a particular culture (Khan and A.N.Ahmad, 2016).

Crime is the subject that interests the social scientists since long. Through research it has been concluded that film is one of the primary source through which people learns and grasps the ideas of the crime (Zedner and Lucia, 2007). Cinematic crime in the media has been a concern for the researchers throughout a significant period. Individuals raise apprehensions about scenes of criminal activities portrayed as heroic ones in movies, TV and different types of media. It impacts the conduct of its audience. Youths nowadays, regularly mirror their good examples aimlessly. What are being featured in media outlets is the bad behaviors and it is portrayed that being good is not enough for being successful and this is portrayed by some very influencing characters in the movies. Media, on their part, frequently grandstand the negativity of an occurrence. It builds up the worthiness of indecencies. The scenes of the crime being appeared in the movies and TV these days have influenced the psyche of people. It is the regular propensity of human conduct to ingest negative things quicker than positive things. What individuals see, is how individuals act. Multiple times, there has been a question mark on the validity of media.

Sheena Rogers is a psychologist and film scholar whose work went further than Dreading's by investigating the connection between film and reality. In her work "Through Alice's Glass: The Creation and Impression of Different Universes in Films, Pictures, and Computer-generated Reality," Rogers talk about the view that individuals who watch films know that there is a distinction between the experience of a movie and the experience of this present reality. This view chips away at the way that when we watch a film, we 'know' it isn't genuine because we are watching it through a screen, yet we are mindful that we are being given pictures of this present reality around us.

Rationale

This research has significant relevance in our society's aspects. First and foremost, an individual who view the serials and get affected through their content is the majority youth. Secondly, it highlights the possible psychological impacts and their actions are influenced through those characters portrayed in the crime series and movies. Lastly, it is valuable for future researchers who study cinematic crime on different Netflix and other web series channels, which progressively influence young people particularly. This is an important topic of study because media is predominant power and gives information to imitate the whole populace and cultivate the good or evil behavior that being copied later on imitated by the young people. A few individuals say that cinematic crimes shown on Netflix (series or movies) are simply amusing and are not intrigued by any stretch of the imagination. This is the matter of seriousness that needs attention for what kind of content is being watched and absorbed by youngsters.

Research Objectives

The principal objectives of this study are:

1. To see how youth is being influenced by cinematic crime appeared in films?
2. To highlight the kind of content individuals watch.
3. To examine that cinematic crime shown on Netflix movies and series is developing soft corners for criminals.
4. To highlight the significance of changing trends of Netflix by portraying evil characters as heroic one and is this long-term agenda of media.

Research Question and Hypothesis:

Q1: Do Crime series shown on Netflix have any effect of the youth of Lahore?

H1: Youth is negatively affected by portrayal of evil characters as heroes on Netflix.

Ho: Youth is not negatively affected by portraying of evil characters as heroic on Netflix.

Literature Review

Media is considered as the reflection of our society that depicts how a certain society works. Media, whether it is print, electronic or web, is required to make people informed. (Nity, 2017). We are living in the hour of data where media is quite possibly the most helpful viewpoint of human existence. We are living in an innovatively progressed world and broad communications are assuming a significant part in our life all things considered administered in each circle of life. The effect of mass communications has expanded dramatically with the improvement in innovation.

Netflix is a web-based streaming supplier that has a huge number of films and projects for watchers from one side of the planet to the other. Netflix streams motion pictures in various dialects, depicting various societies and customs that empower watchers from any spot on the planet to get to know other countries' societies. Today, Netflix typifies the "television All over the place" methodology, watchers can watch Netflix when they need it, how they need it, at any place they need.

Crime or Wrongdoing shows are characterized as a program or dramatization in which examination of wrongdoing or criminal activity appears. Crime films and series isn't another thing in the general public for quite a long time. In the contemporary world, it's difficult to escape from its likenesses with projects, motion pictures, accounts, youngsters' projects, and even plugs (Barlińska et al., 2013).

Violence in the media has expanded driving and extraordinary sorts of brutality in extremely effective movies to decide if savage conduct would amplify barbarities. It is discovered that savagery in the media would influence individuals for the time being, and their arrangement didn't permit them to examine long haul results.

Haridakis and Rubin (2003) uncovered that the majority of individuals normally preferred to watch brutal substance or crime shows for a delight or diversion while considering the substance as an agreeable one, loosening up the program, and a relieving experience as opposed to simply looking for data about the occasion, to learn

anything. As per them, wrongdoing shows having animosity contained what they named, amusement. Crime films have been generally welcomed in the entertainment world; an ever-increasing number of individuals are partaking. Makers are not stressed over the chance of desensitization and dehumanization of the general populace on Earth. Films have extraordinary energy for our adolescence. The marvelous films from the external satisfy them with their insane character. They are so interested and even attempt to have a splendid way of life. This social assault influenced our youth and disregarded our social goodness and strict characteristics. Numerous individuals put their energy to watch motion pictures, utilizing the Web, cell phones and so forth particularly teens, who experience the ill effects of motion pictures. They get what they see on the screen all the more successfully. Because of this choice of downloading, adolescents lose a great deal of time observing motion pictures (Wartella et al., 2016).

The truth can be survived: if the individual starts to live in a universe of accounts, at that point the universe of accounts has become their reality and reality. At present, there is a significant pattern in the motion pictures to show viciousness in light of its TRP. Each film has ruthless conduct that harms youngsters (Jang et al., 2015). Young people are not capable to isolate crime and brutality, all things considered. Our ethical commitment is, hence, to shield young people from openness to unseemly crimes. Tragically, Producers advance crime in their films to incite the youthful brain of young people.

Theoretical Framework

The researcher has chosen Cultivation Theory by George Gerbner for the basis of this research study to examine the “Impact of Cinematic crime (Netflix Series and Movies) on Youth ”because it directly study the effects of media (Netflix) on its viewers (Heavy viewers). The theory is related to media and how it affects its viewers and influence their psychology and research is about how the cinematic crime is shown on Netflix by movies and series affects our youth and how it is changing the trends by portraying evil or criminal activities a heroic one. This negative heroic image is cultivated by youth who eventually end up building negative images of heroes in their mind, their priorities are affected, so their likings. Movies and series like these were the top trending movies of Pakistani Youth which are very alarming situation because in these movies and series, the criminal activities were portrayed as heroic one and according to cultivation theory this behavior can be cultivated in youth and as a result, the criminal activities in the society may increase and affect the peace of the society negatively. Youth make the perception of the negative main characters as the social reality. The continuous exposure to such content may shape their perceptions and this can be insensitive, oppressive, and manipulative.

Research Methodology

According to Kothari (2004), research methodology is a method to analytically explain the research problem. The researcher has used the method of survey to gather research data and it is pure Quantitative Research. The survey method helped gather data that cannot be immediately obtained. An online questionnaire consisting of 15 questions was distributed among youngsters. All the questions were close-ended and related to the objectives. The survey method helps in data collection very conveniently.

The population of this study is the youth who watches Netflix and they are the heavy viewers of the content on Netflix (Movies or Series). The target audience is particularly youth and their perception related to cinematic crime shown in movies and series of Netflix. The sample size is of 100 individuals from different universities. The questionnaire was used as the tool of the survey. The researcher used convenient sampling for this research due to time constraint and lack of funds.

Findings

In the light of the survey conducted the following results were gathered and chalked out as findings.

Table 1

What type of content do you often watch on Netflix?

	FREQUENC Y	PERCENTAG E	COMMULATIV E PERCENATGE
INFORMATIVE	6	6	6
ENTERTAINMEN T	30	30	36
CRIME OR THRILLER	43	43	79
ROMANTIC	9	9	88
ANY OTHER	12	12	100
TOTAL	100	100	

Table 2

Do you think crime series and movies (Lucifer, Money Heist, White tiger etc.) are changing the trends by portraying criminal activities as heroic ones?

	FREQUENCY	PERCENT	COMMULATIVE PERCENTAGE
YES	54	54	54
NO	19	19	73

MAY BE	27	27	100
TOTAL	100	100	

Table 3

Do you feel any change psychologically after watching Netflix Crime related series or movies?

	FREQUENCY	PERCENT	COMMULATIVE PERCENTAGE
YES	40	40	40
NO	37	37	77
MAY BE	23	23	100
TOTAL	100	100	

Table 4

Do you think cinematic crime on Netflix affecting the innocent mindsets of youth?

	FREQUENCY	PERCENT	COMMULATIVE PERCENTAGE
YES	59	59	59
NO	17	17	76
MAY BE	24	24	100
TOTAL	100	100	

Table 5

Is this type of content a long-term agenda of media to normalize the criminal activities in society?

	FREQUENCY	PERCENT	COMMULATIVE PERCENTAGE
YES	49	49	49
NO	23	23	72
MAY BE	28	28	100
TOTAL	100	100	

Table 6

Do you think that this type of content is a threat to youth?

	FREQUENCY	PERCENT	COMMULATIVE PERCENTAGE
YES	59	59	59
NO	17	17	76
MAY BE	24	24	100
TOTAL	100	100	

Table 7

Do you think that it is suitable for youth to watch this type of content?

FREQUENCY	PERCENT	COMMULATIVE PERCENTAGE
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YES	26	26	26
NO	42	42	68
MAY BE	32	32	100
TOTAL	100	100	

Table 8

Do you think that this type of content is developing a soft corner for criminals and their criminal activities?

	FREQUENCY	PERCENT	COMMULATIVE PERCENTAGE
YES	57	57	57
NO	17	17	74
MAY BE	26	26	100
TOTAL	100	100	

Table 9

Do you think Netflix usage negatively affects the psychology of youth?

	FREQUENCY	PERCENT	COMMULATIVE PERCENTAGE
YES	63	63	63
NO	16	16	79
MAY BE	21	21	100
TOTAL	100	100	

Discussion and Analysis

This study “the Impact of Cinematic crime shown on Netflix (Movies and Series) on Youth, the researcher stated four objectives which were the focus points of research throughout the study. The research study shows that content portrayed in the crime movies and serials are positively align to the H1. The criminal content shown in the serials and movies does affect the youth in a negative way.

The first objective refers to investigating the influence of cinematic crime on youth. To determine this objective, the researcher asked few questions and found out in Tables 3, 4, 6, 7 and 9 that they have psychological changes and have a strong impact on their minds after watching violent and criminal content.

The second objective refers to highlighting the importance of the type of content youth watch for the sake of entertainment. To make a conclusion, the researcher crafted few questions and found out in Tables 1,2,6,and 7 that the content youth is watching is not suitable to watch on Netflix ,as a result of that content often starts liking evil and powerful characters and criminal activities as heroic which is an alarming situation.

The next objective refers to investigating if this type of content develops a soft corner for criminals. To determine this objective, the researcher asked three questions and found out in table 3, 5 and 8 that young generation is developing soft corner for criminals and is responsible for criminal activities up to some extent.

The last objective refers to highlight the significance of changing trends on Netflix by portraying criminal activities as heroic and is there any hidden agenda of media in all these situations so researcher asked few questions and found in table 2, 4 and 5 that yes Netflix is changing trends which is alarming and majority believed that there is hidden agenda of media to normalize these criminal activities.

It has been concluded that the cinematic crime shown on Netflix (Movies and series) do have a negative impact on youth. The hypothesis “Youth is negatively affected by portraying of evil characters as heroic one on Netflix.” **is accepted** as it has been proved that the cinematic crime shown on Netflix (Movies and series) do have a negative impact on youth.

Conclusion

The research title "Impact of Cinematic crime shown on Netflix (Movies and Series) on Youth" aims to investigate the negative portrayal of heroes in movies and series shown on Netflix that portrays criminal activities as heroic and to check the influence of such content on the perception of youth and to investigate how it influences young people. Mass communication is an integral asset that can serve both good and evil and for the most part talking, if it's anything but sufficiently controlled, it might be harmful. The fundamental method of learning for youngsters is perception and impersonation. Confronted with a cinematic crime in the film or series, they can't recognize the rightness of things, so it is not difficult to copy in the wake of watching the film, and some will show up, in reality. Youngsters' musings are as yet during the time spent developing, and qualities have not yet been full-fledged. The makers of the film should focus closer on the gatherings of youngsters and make film and series that turns out reasonable for them. They should bear the social ascribes and duties of engaging and helping young people construct positive qualities and well-beings brain science. It has been proved that the cinematic crime shown on Netflix (Movies and series) do have a negative impact on youth.

Recommendations

- The content creators should show the stories with positive characters and positive heroic activities to give the audience a positive message so that the audience cultivates positive aspects of it and ultimately it benefits the society.
- They should think out of the box and should give wider view of the world by keeping in view that media has long term effects on its audience so that the content should be produced with responsibility.
- Young generation should be conscious enough to decide what content they should be watching for the sake of entertainment.

Limitations

- This research had considered a small sample of 100 respondents male and female, to examine the impact of Cinematic crime shown on Netflix (Movies and Series) on Youth, which is not enough to represent the entire universe of Netflix viewers.
- This research focuses on the youth from the age 15 to 25 years according to the definition of WHO, that's why the age group is limited. The research is limited to the survey.

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